

The Chemical Elements and Compounds *

By SIR P. C. RAY, Kt., C.I.E., DSc., Ph.D.

Our ideas of the nature and properties of the elementary atoms and their compounds have undergone profound changes as the result of the most important investigations in physical science during the last two decades. The old simple Daltonian conception of atoms as the ultimate indivisible particles with constant weights can no longer be accepted without reservations. Every student of physical science now learns that an atom is a very complicated structure resembling the solar system with a positively charged central nucleus --the seat of the entire weight of the atom--surrounded by a number of electrons or negative units of electricity moving rapidly in definite circular and elliptical orbits. This modern Rutherford-Bohr model of atom has invaded our chemical science and a host of eminent workers are busy in illuminating many obscure branches of chemistry, systematising and unifying the entangled mass of uncoordinated facts,—in other words, building cosmos out of chaos—specially in the inorganic branch of chemistry which has suffered so long from the reproach of being simply a collection of dull and insipid facts with no underlying theoretical basis.

The most fundamental problem of chemistry which has engaged the serious attention of the chemists since the enunciation of Daltonian hypothesis, is the combining power or the valency of the atom. The cause of this combining power and its variability has long remained in the dark in spite of numerous hypotheses and speculations on the subject. But since the development of the modern atomic structure, entirely new light has been thrown on it and it is hoped that in no distant future the chemists will be in a position to unravel this fundamental mystery of their science and even to predict the nature and properties of unknown compounds just as they have done with

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the unknown elements of which the discovery of hafnium furnishes a striking instance. Notable progress has already been made in this direction and several theories of valency—and I must admit that some of them of even conflicting nature—are trying to establish and hold their position in the chemical literature. The most generally accepted view as has been developed by Kossel, Lewis, Langmuir and Sidgwick can briefly be summarised as follows :

The elementary atoms are not all equally stable. Hence they readily combine with other atoms or even with themselves to form what are known as compounds or simple molecules. There are, however, only a few elements represented by the rare gases of the atmosphere whose atoms fail to exhibit any such tendency for combination. Their atoms are regarded as chemically and electrically inert. Hence it is assumed that the atoms of these monatomic gases represent the most stable configurations in the evolution of the elements. All the other elementary atoms, whose structures are comparatively less stable, tend to attain the stable configuration representing their nearest rare-gas neighbour by mutual union. This is regarded as the ultimate cause of chemical combination. The atoms just preceding the rare-gas elements in the natural series of elements can do this by accepting one or more electrons from others and the atoms just succeeding the rare-gases stabilize their configurations by transferring or giving up one or more electrons to their partners in the chemical combination. This exchange, transfer or sharing of electrons are confined to the outermost layer of the atom. These are therefore known as valency electrons.

Two main types of valency are generally recognized. These are *polar* or *electro-valency* and *non-polar* or *co-valency*. Polar bonds lead to the formation of ions by transfer of electrons as in the case of NaCl; non-polar or co-valent bonds lead to the formation of non-ionized molecules by sharing of electrons such as Cl_2 , O_2 , SO_2 , CH_4 etc. The formation of an outermost eight-electronic layer as the result of chemical combination has given rise to the name of the *Octet Theory of Valency* as was first developed by Lewis and Langmuir, since an outermost layer of eight electrons is a characteristic feature of the atoms of the rare-gas elements. Each electrovalent bond consists in the transfer or acceptance of an electron by the atom; the atoms which transfer or part with electrons are therefore called *electropositive* and those which receive the electron are termed *electronegative*. Each co-valent bond consists

in the sharing of a pair of electrons. Co-valencies are again subdivided into *normal co-valency* and *co-ordinate co-valency* according to Sidgwick. In normal co-valency each atom contributes one electron to the shared pair and in the co-ordinate co-valency both the shared electrons come from one of the combining atoms. This latter is assumed to explain the formation of complex ions and compounds of the Werner-type.

This modern electronic theory of valency, though capable of offering a satisfactory explanation for a large variety of chemical combinations and even predicting the course of the reaction in certain spheres of organic chemistry, is yet far from attaining its perfection. Instances are not rare where it signally fails. Some of these exceptions will be discussed presently.

We can classify our chemical compounds under two main heads.

1. Compounds of the first order or the so-called simple compounds. This includes the organic compounds as well.
2. Compounds of the second order which can again be sub-divided into—

- (a) Double salts and hydrates, and
- (b) Complex salts.

Among the compounds of the first order we have got both homo-polar and hetero-polar compounds characterised by the manifestation of co-valency and electro-valency. Exceptions that can be cited under this head are—

Some of these cases, as is well known, have long attracted the attention of the workers in this field; and several suggestions have been made to explain the mechanism of their formation. But it must be admitted that they have failed to improve the situation. The cases of sulphur fluoride and phosphorus halides have long been thoroughly discussed. And unless we assume them to be hetero-polar with sulphur as a hexavalent positive ion and phosphorus as a pentavalent one, which cannot be justified from the behaviour of the substances themselves, there is no other way of representing them on the basis of the electronic theory of valency. The case of boron hydride is still an unsolved problem in spite of numerous electronic constitutions suggested for it. The cases of BrF_3 and IF_5 are still in a worse position. Their formation can in no way be accounted

for either on the basis of electro-valency or co-valency. Why should bromine or iodine atom with seven peripheral electrons should part or share with three or five more electrons is beyond any reasonable explanation. The fluorine molecules, on the other hand, can never be made to attach themselves to a fluorine atom with its completed octet on the basis of our modern hypothesis. The same difficulties are met with in the case of I_3 -ion as well.

Evidently considerations of some other factors besides the sharing or transfer of electrons must be made in order to explain the mechanism of chemical combination. Whether it is of the nature of an electrostatic or magnetic attraction, we are not yet in a position to affirm. Study of the molecular structure by the physicists, it is hoped, will furnish us ere long with the solution of all these difficulties.

Passing on to the compounds of the second order—the hydrates and the double salts—we encounter the same difficulties again. Why should KCl , $MgCl_2$ and H_2O molecules which according to modern hypothesis all possess stable and completed structure, combine again to form a complicated molecule known as carnallite $KCl, MgCl_2, 6H_2O$ cannot be easily explained unless we assume some sort of electrostatic attraction between the ions.

Finally the so-called complex compounds of the Werner-type present entirely a new aspect of the problem. Here unlike in double salts and hydrates, we find that the properties of the component molecules undergo a profound modification in the complex formed just as we meet with in the case of the compounds of the first order. It must be noted here however that there is no sharp demarcation between the complex and the double salts. The transition between them is gradual and insensible. Even among the well-known complexes we find different degree of stability. Some are quite stable in solution, the others are not. The most characteristic complex compounds are formed by the elements of the transitional group of the Bohr's periodic system. Even these exhibit a great difference in properties. For example, whereas the simple cobaltous and cobaltic salts are strongly paramagnetic, the complex cobaltic salts on the other hand, are diamagnetic. Simple nickel salts and most of the complex nickel salts possess almost the same paramagnetic susceptibility. But there are certain complex nickel-compounds such as $K_2Ni(CN)_4$, nickel-dimethylglyoxime and nickel-dicyandiamidine which are diamagnetic.

Evidently here also we find indications of the existence of two types of complex compounds. One of my colleagues in my laboratory has named them "perfect" and "imperfect complexes." The question now arises—does this indicate two different types of combination? It has already been stated that a co-ordination bond like a co-valent bond is due to the sharing of a pair of electrons between the co-ordinating ion and each co-ordinated partner only with this difference that in a co-ordination bond both the electrons of the pair come from the co-ordinated atom. Again the number of co-ordination valency, or co-ordination number as it is called, that an atom usually manifests is either four or six. What determines this number is not quite clear. According to Magnus it is the size and the charge of the central co-ordinating ion which regulate this number assuming that the ions or atoms are spherical in shape. The larger is the size of the co-ordinating atom the larger is its co-ordination number as it can accommodate larger number of co-ordinated partners around its surface.

Suggestions have also been made by Welo, Baudisch, and others that in the formation of complex compounds the central co-ordinating atom tends to assume the next inert gas configuration by accepting electrons from the co-ordinated partners. This holds good only in the cases of cobaltic, iridic, rhodic and platinumic complexes and in certain ferrous, molybdenum and tungsten complexes. Thus :

	Electron number.	Co-ordination number.	Total electron.
Co ³⁺	24	6	36 (Krypton structure)
Ir ³⁺	74	6	86 (Niton ..)
Pt ⁴⁺	74	6	86
Bh ³⁺	42	6	54 (Xenon ..)
Fe ²⁺ (ferrocyanides)	24	6	36 (Krypton ..)
Mo ²⁺ (molybdicyanides)	38	8	54 (Xenon ..)
W ²⁺ (tungsticyanides)	70	8	86 (Niton ..)

Each co-ordination number or bond supplies two electrons as has already been stated.

Curiously enough all these complexes which thus assume the inert-gas structure are diamagnetic. All the other complexes formed

by nickel, ferric iron, chromium, palladium, osmium, manganese, tri- and penta-valent molybdenum and tungsten, bivalent platinum, bivalent cobalt, etc., fail to comply with this requirement (formation of inert-gas structure).

It has already been pointed out that the complexes can be conveniently classified into "perfect" and "imperfect" types. It may be assumed as one of my colleagues has already done that in the "perfect" type actual sharing of electrons takes place forming the so-called co-ordination bonds. In the "imperfect" type which may be regarded as forming the transition between the "perfect" complexes and the double salts, the bond is due to some sort of electrostatic or electromagnetic attraction between the co-ordinating atom and the co-ordinated partners which usually possess a dipole moment.

In this connection one may enquire why only some of the members of the transitional elements are peculiarly suited for the formation of complex compounds. Why among the neighbouring elements Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, and Ni,—it is Co and Cr and to certain extent Fe and Ni that easily form complexes? In manganese however this property of complex building is only very slightly developed. Further it is known that boron forms stable boron trifluoride and boron trichloride. But whereas boron trifluoride easily combines with HF and metallic fluorides to form quite stable complex fluoborates, boron trichloride fails to manifest any such capacity to combine with hydrochloric acid and chlorides. Similarly potassium silicofluorides and potassium titanifluorides represent quite stable complexes whereas the corresponding chlorides are unknown. This difference of behaviour between chlorine and fluorine is inexplicable. This and several other similar difficulties still await a satisfactory explanation.

Further there are many so-called complex salts which are known only in the solid condition. They break up as soon as they pass into aqueous solution. We, therefore, find that the strength of the valency-bond gradually diminishes as we pass from the simple compounds to complex and double salts. And we may reasonably assume that this finally degenerates or weakens into the so-called lattice-force in the crystal structure. The molecules in the crystal are held together by a force which vanishes rapidly as the crystal either passes into the solution or melts or if it sublime into gaseous condition. The only attractive force between

the molecules in the latter conditions is what is known as Van der Waal's attraction. It is not difficult to perceive a qualitative unity in this diverse manifestation of attractive or combining forces ranging between Van der Waal's attraction at the one end and the sharing or transfer of electrons at the other. Many of the so-called absorption-compounds represent the transition between the true chemical combination and physical agglomeration.

Finally the case of a type of compounds known as intermetallic compounds may be here conveniently discussed. In a true metallic element the binding between the atoms is neither polar nor unpolar. It seems to represent a transition between the two. The metallic atoms possess a strong tendency to part with their outermost loosely-bound electrons and thus become positive ions of stable configuration. When two such atoms approach each other, the loosely-bound valence-electrons of both tend to leave their original owners; but as neither of the combining atom would tolerate any excess of electrons in their own sphere, these binding electrons simply vibrate between the two atomic cores. They cannot enclose the nuclei of the combining atoms as in homopolar bindings. This differentiates the metallic binding from co-valency. In the formation of true intermetallic compounds therefore we do not meet any valence-regularity. Compounds of composition are formed which do not correspond to our usual valence-conception of the combining atoms. Compounds of the type Cd_3Na , Ca_4Zn , LiHg_3 , NaHg_4 , etc., are not rare among them. Evidently quite different factors dominate the formation of true inter-metallic compounds. It appears that the size of the atoms determines more or less the nature of the compounds formed. We shall see later on that the same volume-factor also determines to a great extent the crystal-form built by the elements and compounds. Consequently the binding force in the inter-metallic compounds resembles what prevails between the building stones of a crystal unit.

Only in those cases where there is a sensible polar difference between the partners of intermetallic compounds conditions of valency are found to be fulfilled, *e.g.*, in Ag_3Sb , As_2Cd_3 , etc.

We have so long discussed the chemical properties of the elements and compounds and have sought to trace the cause and origin thereof. The question that naturally arises next is what determines the physical properties of the elements and their compounds. Just as

in the case of the chemical properties the outermost valency-electrons are also responsible for the physical properties of the atoms. But, strictly speaking, it is the size or volume of the atom or the ion that mainly determines these properties. Of course the volume of the atom is related to the position of the valency electrons. The properties of diffusion, refraction, crystal-form, ionisation potential and isomorphous replacibility are closely connected with the atomic or ionic radii. Of all these, I shall confine myself only to the crystal-form and isomorphous replacibility, being the most important physical properties from the chemist's point of view.

Goldschmidt who has been working on crystal-chemistry for several years and to whom we are indebted for the signal advancement in this branch of science, sums up the determining factors in crystal-formation in the following words :

"The structure of a crystal is determined by the ratio of numbers, the ratio of sizes and the properties of polarization of its building stones. As the building stones of crystals we visualise atoms, ions or groups of atoms."

By polarization is meant the deformation of the electronic orbits of the anion by the cation which undoubtedly affects the volume relationship.

Mitscherlich's law of isomorphism, which had played such an important part in the development of our science specially regarding the determination of atomic weights, finds an easy explanation in the light of above conclusions. Mitscherlich discovered that two substances which are homeomorphous and form mixed crystals are isomorphous and possess analagous chemical formulae. Its explanation is now quite clear. But the reverse is not always true, *i.e.*, all substances having the same type of chemical formulæ are not isomorphous; because, as Goldschmidt has deduced, analogy is required not only as to the numbers but also as to the "properties" of particles such as the relative size and properties of polarisation.

Isomorphism is primarily related to the atomic or ionic volume and many puzzling and anomalous cases of isomorphism observed by Barker, Goldschmidt and others have now been easily explained. I shall here deal with one very interesting case of isomorphism which was noticed by Barker but has recently been thoroughly worked out in all details in my laboratory by two of my colleagues. I mean the isomorphism of fluoberyllates and sulphates. It has been shown that all fluoberyllates form mixed crystals with their corresponding

sulphates. The analogy extends even to the double sulphates. The following fluoberyllates have been prepared and studied by them :

A_2BeF_4 where $A = NH_4, Li, Na, K, Rb$ and Cs isomorphous with corresponding sulphates. $(NH_4)_2BeF_4 \cdot M_2SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $(NH_4)_2BeF_4 \cdot M_2BeF_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ isomorphous with $(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot M_2SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, where $M = Ni, Co, Zn, Mn, Cd, Cu, Fe''$ and Mg .

Now if we assume that sulphur atom in SO_4 is hexavalent and positive, beryllium in BeF_4 is bivalent and positive then we find that their ionic radii according to Goldschmidt are exactly identical being equal to $0.94A^\circ$. Similarly fluorine ion and oxygen ion have ionic radii equal to $1.93A^\circ$ and $1.92A^\circ$ respectively. Further the number of particles in the two complex radicles is the same and the nature and value of their charges are also the same. Hence it can be easily expected from Goldschmidt's principle that they will exhibit close isomorphous relationships. It has further been shown that the analogy between these two types of compounds extends to many other physical properties due to their isosteric and isoelectric nature.

The isomorphous replacibility of K and Rb by (NH_4) , isomorphism of KNO_3 and $CaCO_3$, LiF and MgO , and of KBF_4 and $KClO_4$ can also be accounted for on the same basis. In ammonium ion we find a radicle possessing isomorphous relationships with metallic ions like K and Rb . This has been possible because their ionic radii are very much alike.

So we are now in a position to affirm that the physical properties of the elements and compounds are mostly determined by the relative sizes of their atoms or the corresponding ions.

In this brief discussion I have attempted to indicate the recent progress in our knowledge of the properties of chemical elements and compounds. And in conclusion I would like to express our indebtedness for many of the recent advancements in this branch of our science to our non-chemist colleagues—specially the physicists who have been able to establish on a firm and theoretical basis many of our empirical assumptions and hypotheses.*

* For many of the ideas elaborated in this paper I am deeply indebted to Mr. P. B. Ray of the University College of Science, Calcutta.

